

JOB MOTIVATION LEVEL FOR ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS WHO MADE FIELD CHANGES

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Abstract:

The aim of this research is to determine the job motivation levels of primary school teachers who have made or have had to make field changes due to the new education system (4+4+4). The sample of the research consists of 512 teachers working in primary and secondary schools in Balıkesir province in 2016-2017. The data needed for the research were obtained through the Job Motivation Scale that consisted of 18 items in accordance with the survey research model in quantitative research methods. In the analysis of the data, techniques such as Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) were used. As a result of the research, significant differences were found in organizational-managerial and psycho-social dimensions of job motivation in terms of gender, school type and field change.

Keywords: job motivation, 4+4+4 education system, teacher, field change

1. Introduction

It is an undeniable fact that organizations must adapt to the constantly changing environment in order for them to continue their lives. Educational organizations, like every organization, are also affected by these changes in their surroundings. The closest example is the introduction of the new education system known as 4+4+4 in 2012-2013 academic year and 12 years of compulsory education. In the new system, students are

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required to attend primary school for the first four years, secondary school for the second four years and high school for the last four years (Güven, 2012). In addition, the age of starting school was reduced to enforce compulsory primary school age children in the 6-13 age group (Yıldırım, 2013).

One of the main objectives of educational organizations is to increase the performance of teachers and to ensure that their goals are carried out efficiently. However, teachers need to be motivated first to improve their performance. Because employees with low motivation do not or cannot use the entire capacity (Örücüler & Kambur, 2008, Sezer, 2012). Research shows that motivation is important not only in educational organizations but also in other organizations. When the researches made in recent years are examined, it is seen that job motivation is subject to many studies and its relation with different organizational variables is examined. These variables related to job motivation can be given as examples; organizational climate (Aksoy, 2006), participatory school culture (Tanrıverdi, 2007), emotional commitment (Ağca & Ertan, 2008), job satisfaction (Toker, 2006; Yavuz & Karadeniz, 2009), organizational culture (Yılmaz, 2009), stress factors (Şenel, 2011), organizational commitment (Oran, 2012), performance management in organizations (Mercanlıoğlu, 2012), employee performance and intent to leave work (Yıldız, Savcı, & Kapu, 2014), organizational health (Güçlü, Reçepoğlu, & Kılınç, 2014), organizational justice (Abbasoğlu, 2015). Robins and Judge (2013) described motivation as a power felt within a person, which activate the person for a certain purpose, direct to work, and increase the desire to work on the person. In this context, job motivation can be defined as an important phenomenon in organizational behavior as a factor that directs and influences the behavior of employees (Örücü & Kambur, 2008). The lack of effectiveness and productivity of the employees who are at the head of today's problems arises from the fact that employees cannot be motivated enough internally or externally. If employees, no matter how well equipped they are, cannot be motivated and if their performances are not fairly assessed or they think this way, the required efficiency cannot be obtained from the worker (Tunçer, 2013).

In this research, it will be examined whether the gender, school type and field variables of the teachers who change the field due to the new system working in elementary and junior high school affect the job motivations.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Job Motivation

Motivation is an important phenomenon that enables organizations to be successful, improve and sustain their existence. In addition, motivation problems are one of the

most frequently encountered problems of organizational managers. Among the motivation problems encountered within the organization, there are insufficient efforts of the employees, constant fatigue, frequent absenteeism, and lack of desire to work (Aksoy, 2006). The fact that motivation is a psychological phenomenon causes to be addressed from different angles and to produce different definitions (Karakaya & Ay, 2007). When these definitions are examined, Sabuncuoğlu and Tüz (2008) defined motivation as a driving force and factor affecting to move in a certain way or to prefer the motion path to others; Reçpoğlu (2013) expressed motivation as our desire from within us, a desire to do something. According to Başaran (2004), motivation is to make an effort for a purpose and sustain this effort. Along with this, Hoy and Miskel (2010) defined motivation as an internal process that usually moves, directs and sustains behavior. Motivation is not a directly observable structure. The level of motivation of the individual can be determined by verbal expression, preference among the targets, and indirectly observable behavior sequences. Motivation leads people to understand why people are acting in specific ways (Aktan & Tezci, 2013). In the direction of motivation definitions, job motivation can be defined as the willingness of employees to work in the direction of organizational goals and the search and formation of necessary conditions to be productive (Karakaya & Ay, 2007). When other definitions of job motivation are examined, Örucü and Kambur (2008) expressed job motivation as a factor that significantly influences, directs and causes employee behaviors in an organization; Ağca and Ertan (2008) described job motivation as the willingness to spend effort at the high level to pursue organizational goals.

Among the reasons for the decline in motivation, which is one of the important elements of management psychology, the shift to automation and mass production in especially advanced industrial societies takes place today. Reduction of human labor and automatic machining of jobs cause employees not to enjoy the work they do and to address the need to create something new. Another important factor in the reduction of employee motivation is that there is a gap between the upper and lower levels in large organizations and the lack of communication causes the employees to be reluctant. Employees who cannot participate in the decisions made can be observed to be lazy over time. Due to these reasons, organizational managers are having a great deal of work and need to motivate their employees with some motivation tools (Eren, 2015). According to Efil (2009), while managers motivate their employees, they should encourage them by providing the necessary values, encourage successful employees, encourage employees to improve themselves, treat them equally and criticize without humiliating them, be an example to employees, and try to find common solutions in the case of failures (as cited in Tunçer, 2013). Because, employees who receive management support will be more willing to focus on success and to solve problems. Also, the

motivation and success of employees who adapt to the organization and support organizational values also increase (Öztürk & Dündar, 2003). Systems that enable interaction, grouping, and flow of information steadily reach their environment and can effectively use information to counter disruptions arising from external and internal volatility (Marion, Christiansen, Klar, Schreiber & Erdener, 2016). Tezci and Gürol (2003) emphasize that individuals improve themselves in the environments that activate their internal motivations, do not judge their evaluation approaches, and raise their curiosity. There is a positive relationship between motivation and the support that the family, friend environment and special individuals give to the person (Tezci, Sezer, Gürkan, & Aktan, 2015).

Organizational managers should take into account motivation theories as well as paying attention to motivational tools and motivational principles to increase employee motivation. Motivation theories in literature are examined under two headings, scope and process theories. According to the scope theory, if motivation is to be provided at a workplace, an environment that meets the needs of employees must be created. In an organization, if there are absenteeism, poor performance and effort, negative attitudes and behaviors towards the organization, then the underlying reason is dissatisfaction of the needs of employees (Schermerhorn, Hunt & Osborn, 2002). When the scope theories are examined; Abraham Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory, Herzberg's Motivation Theory, Alderfer's ERG Theory, and McClland's Human Motivation Theory are the most emerging theories. The driving point of process theories is to determine how motivated individuals are for what purpose. The main difference that distinguishes process theories from scope theories is that, process theories attach more importance to individual differences (Eren, 2015). In process theories; Vroom's Expectation Theory, Adams's Reward Justice and Equity Theory, Reinforcement Theory, and Edwin A. Locke's Goal-Setting Theory stand out. In this research, necessary studies will be done based on Edwin A. Locke's Goal-Setting Theory.

2.2. Edwin A. Locke's Goal-Setting Theory

It is seen that in the 1950s and 1960s, motivation was within the field of behavioral scientists. Later studies have shown that motivation is primarily a psychological rather than a behavioral phenomenon. In the 1970s, T. A. Ryan showed that behaviors have been influenced by conscious purposes such as plans, intentions, tasks etc. At the root of the determining, a goal lies the premise that Ryan's conscious goals influence the individual's actions. Goals have a significant impact on the behavior and performance of employees in organizations and management practices (Locke & Latham, 2002). For this reason, managers should agree to set targets to improve and sustain employee performance (Dubrin, 2012).

Edwin Locke, the pioneer of the goal-setting theory, included approximately 400 studies in his study. According to Locke, there are two cognitive determinants that determine an individual's behavior. These are values and intentions, which is goals. The goal can be defined as what the individual consciously tries to do. The values of the individual are emotional and lead the individual to demonstrate consistent behaviors. Goals also influence the behavior of the individual through other mechanisms. For this reason, the goals for Locke attract the attention of the individual and direct him to action. By activating the energy in the individual, the difficulty of the goal leads the individual to spend more effort and apply different strategies to reach the goal. Ultimately, achieving the goal can increase the satisfaction and motivation, while failing to achieve the goal can cause disappointment and reduced motivation (Lunenburg, 2011).

The Goal-Setting Theory is a theory that only focuses on goal setting. These goals are the goals that the individual sets in relation to his work. These goals that the individual determines may be the goals that the employee sets for himself or may be the goals that the organization assigns to the employees individually who work towards the general objectives of the organization. As a result, these business-related goals have certain characteristics (Onaran, 1981). These features are:

- The goals/objectives should be clearly defined. The generalization of the objectives or the lack of clear understanding by the employees can negatively affect the performance. In addition, the views of the employees should be taken when the goal is determined. This increases the employee's commitment to the goals and the desire to achieve them.
- Difficult goals/objectives provide greater performance than easy goals.
- Feedback should be given to the employees regarding the results. Because, the employee wants to know where he is to become motivated and how much more effort he has to spend to reach his goal.
- Care must be taken to ensure that the objective is achievable when it is determined. If the employee believes that the goal is unachievable, then both the motivation and the performance of the employee are reduced (Schermerhorn, Hunt & Osborn, 2002).

Given the above basic characteristics, we can express Goal-Setting Theory as follows:

Figure 1: Goal-setting theory

Source: Hoy, W. K., & Miskel, C. G. (2010). *Eğitim yönetimi teori, araştırma ve uygulama* (7. press) (Transl. Selahattin Turan). İstanbul: Nobel Yayınları, p.141

When Figure 1 is examined, the Goal-Setting Theory should primarily set explicit, challenging, and extensive but achievable goals/objectives. This is because these types of goals, by drawing attention of employees, ensure the development and application of strategies that are appropriate for effort, insistence, persistence, and the goal. Providing feedback on the performance shown in order to achieve the goal also strengthen the effort, insistence, and persistence of employee and also allows the development or renewal of the strategy used (Hoy & Miskel, 2010).

As a result of hundreds of studies, it appears that employees with explicit, challenging but achievable goals perform better than employees with inexplicit and easy goals, or without goals. In addition, employees must have adequate competence, adopt goals, and receive feedback on their performance (Latham, 2003). The Goal-Setting Theory assumes that individuals consciously choose their goals. But individuals may not always set their goals consciously; they may choose to act without conscious thought and without thinking too much. However, the perception and valuation variables that arise as a result of individual differences may also vary according to individual judgments and emotions. For this reason, it is very difficult to implement managerial policies by determining individual goals individually. In spite of all these, it is possible to say that this is a theory that can guide the managers to combine the goals of the individuals and the goals of the organization (Eren, 2015).

3. Material and Methods

3.1. Research Model

In this study, the survey research design was used in order to describe the effects of the application of 4+4+4 education system on primary and secondary school teachers' motivation in terms of various variables. Screening research is a research approach on large masses in order to describe the past or present situation (Büyüköztürk, Çakmak, Akgün, Karadeniz & Demirel, 2014). The purpose of the screening studies is to ensure that the investigated situation is accurately presented. In this study, the effects of gender, school type and field variables of primary and secondary school teachers on job motivations were examined.

3.2. Participants

The universe of the research is composed of teachers working in elementary and secondary schools affiliated to the Ministry of National Education in the province of Balıkesir in the academic year of 2016-2017. The sample of the study consists of 512 teachers in 25 schools determined by simple random sampling in the province of Balıkesir. The data were collected during the fall semester of the 2016-2017 academic year. In this context, out of the survey instruments distributed to the teachers in 25 schools, 587 were returned and 512 were analyzed because 75 of them were incomplete. Of the 512 participant teachers, 294 (57.4%) were female and 218 (42.6%) were male. Of the 512 participant teachers, 251 (49%) were in primary school and 261 (51%) were in secondary school. In addition, 32 teachers participating in the survey stated that they made field changes.

3.3. Data Collection Tools

In this research, "Job Motivation Scale" developed by Aksoy (2006) was used to determine job motivation levels of teachers working in primary and secondary schools. Aksoy (2006) has developed this instrument in one dimension. The Job Motivation Scale was adapted by Tanrıverdi (2007) to the education organizations in one dimension and Cronbach's alpha value was calculated as $\alpha = .90$. Deniz and Erdener (2016) examined two sub-dimensions of organizational-managerial motivation and psycho-social motivation as a result of exploratory factor analysis for the Job Motivation Scale. According to Deniz and Erdener (2016), Cronbach's alpha value for the organizational-managerial motivation subscale was calculated as $\alpha = .91$ and $\alpha = .94$ for the psycho-social motivation subscale. A 5-point Likert type scale was used to determine the job motivation levels of the teachers and the options were rated as "very dissatisfied,

dissatisfied, neither, satisfied, very satisfied" (1-5) from the most negative to the most positive.

3.4. Data Analysis

For the statistical analysis of 512 scales collected and evaluated within the scope of the research, SPSS 24 package program used in data analysis as it is used social sciences. First, to determine demographic characteristics, descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, and so on were calculated, afterwards to determine the distribution of the data the kurtosis and skewness tests were used. Data analysis has progressed in two steps. In the first step, the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was used to examine whether the functions of the Job Motivation Scale showed two-factorial and 18-item structure as predicted by Deniz and Erdener (2016), and whether the subscale correlations with the factors fit the expected structure. As a result of the CFA, it was determined that the Job Motivation Scale is composed of two sub-dimensions and 18 items as in Deniz and Erdener (2016). In the second step, Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) was conducted to determine whether teachers' attitudes towards job motivations differ significantly according to gender, teaching stage and field change variables (Mertler & Vannaatta, 2010). MANOVA has been chosen to investigate possible differences between independent variables (Huck, 2011). Plots were used in place of the Post-Hoc LSD test of multivariate comparison tests to determine the source of possible differences between variables, as each of the three independent variables consisted of two different groups. A $p < 0.05$ significance level was considered in interpreting the results. In addition, Levene's test results were examined to see if there was a linear relationship between the variables and the homogeneity of variance-covariance matrices, and the results showed a normal distribution with the necessary essential conditions.

4. Results

4.1. Factor Analysis

In this study, Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was used to examine whether teachers' job motivations showed a two-factorial and 18-item structure as predicted by Deniz and Erdener (2016) and whether sub-dimensions correlated with the expected structure. The fit indices used in testing the validity of the factor structures and the correctness of the model and the values related to these indices are described in Table 1.

Table 1: Fit Indices and Values for Confirmatory Factor Analysis

	Fit Indices	Values	Decision
χ^2		288.65	
sd		126	
χ^2/sd	<3= Perfect	2.29	Accepted
GFI	>.95= Perfect	0.90	Accepted
AGFI	>.90 (AGFI).95< =	0.87	Accepted
CFI	>.95= Perfect	0.98	Accepted
NFI	>.95= Perfect	0.98	Accepted
NNFI	>.95= Perfect	0.97	Accepted
SRMR	<.05= Perfect	0.046	Accepted
RMR	>.05=RMR<.081= Acceptable	0.054	Accepted
RMSEA	<.05= Perfect	0.066	Accepted
RFI	>.95= Perfect	0.96	Accepted
IFI	>.95= Perfect	0.98	Accepted

It is possible to say that all the values obtained in Table 1 are suitable for analysis when looking at the values formed in the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) result. In addition to this, it was determined that the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) applied resulted in a total of two sub-dimensions and 18 items, as adapted by Deniz and Erdener (2016). While the items 3, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 13, 15, 16, 17, and 18 expresses the "psycho-social motivation", the items 1, 2, 4, 5, 10, 12, and 14 expresses "organizational-managerial motivation".

4.2. Multivariate Analysis of Variance

After the factor analysis, dimensions of "organizational-managerial motivation" and "psycho-social motivation" belonging to the Job Motivation Scale were considered as dependent variables. Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) was then conducted to determine whether instructional leadership behaviors that school principals exhibit during classroom supervision differ significantly from the independent variables of gender, school type, and field change. The output of MANOVA involves the homogeneity test of variances. Therefore, comments start with the results of the Box test (Mertler & Vannaatta, 2010). The Box's M test values, which are the result of the analysis made, are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Box's M Multivariate Analysis Test

Box's Test of Equality of Covariance Matrices	
Box's M	43,197
F	2,291
df1	18
df2	8619,014
Sig.	.001

Note: Tests the null hypothesis that the observed covariance matrices of the dependent variables are equal across groups.

According to the results of Box's M variance equality test (Box's M=18, 8619.014; F=2.291, p=.001), covariance equality was not accepted. The Pillai's Trace test was preferred because of a significant difference in Box's M test for testing covariance matrix equality. The homogeneity of the variance-covariance matrices which are one of the basic conditions for the multivariate analyses and whether there is a linear relationship between the variables is also examined according to Levene's test results and it is determined that it has the necessary basic conditions. Table 3 presents the results of the Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA) test to determine whether teachers differ significantly according to the variables such as gender, school type and field change depending on the job motivation.

Table 3: Multivariate Analysis of Variance of the Job Motivation Scale

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	p	η^2
Intercept	Pillai's	,942	4126,344 ^b	2,000	504,000	,000	,942
	Trace						
Gender	Pillai's	,015	3,710 ^b	2,000	504,000	,025	,015
	Trace						
SchoolLevel	Pillai's	,012	3,048 ^b	2,000	504,000	,048	,012
	Trace						
FieldChanged	Pillai's	,015	3,786 ^b	2,000	504,000	,023	,015
	Trace						
Gender * SchoolLevel	Pillai's	,002	,439 ^b	2,000	504,000	,645	,002
	Trace						
Gender * FieldChanged	Pillai's	,016	4,043 ^b	2,000	504,000	,018	,016
	Trace						
SchoolLevel * FieldChanged	Pillai's	,002	,593 ^b	2,000	504,000	,553	,002
	Trace						
Gender * SchoolLevel * FieldChanged	Pillai's	,000	. ^b	,000	,000	.	.
	Trace						

a. Design: Intercept + Gender + SchoolLevel + FieldChanged + Gender * SchoolLevel + Gender * FieldChanged + SchoolLevel * FieldChanged + Gender * SchoolLevel * FieldChanged

b. Exact statistic

Based on the teachers' gender, [Pillai's Trace = 0.015, $F(2, 504) = 3.710$, $p = 0.025$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.015$], school type [Pillai's Trace = 0.012, $F(2, 504) = 3.048$, $p = 0.048$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.012$], and field change [Pillai's Trace = 0.015, $F(2, 504) = 3.786$, $p = 0.023$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.015$], there is a significant difference on their job motivation.

In addition, based on the teachers' gender*field change [Pillai's Trace = 0.016, $F(2, 504) = 4.043$, $p = 0.018$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.016$], there is a significant difference on the job motivation of teachers; however, based on gender*school type [Pillai's Trace = 0.002, $F(2, 504) = .439$, $p = 0.645$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.002$] and school type*field change [Pillai's Trace = 0.002, $F(2, 504) = .593$, $p = 0.553$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.002$], there is no significant difference on their job motivation.

Table 4: MANOVA Results for Job Motivation

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	η^2
Corrected Model	Organizational	,100 ^a	6	,017	3,336	,003	,038
	Psycho-Social	,147 ^b	6	,025	2,586	,018	,030
Intercept	Organizational	39,701	1	39,701	7949,452	,000	,940
	Psycho-Social	32,501	1	32,501	3422,480	,000	,871
Gender	Organizational	,002	1	,002	,433	,511	,001
	Psycho-Social	,012	1	,012	1,294	,256	,003
SchoolLevel	Organizational	,004	1	,004	,867	,352	,002
	Psycho-Social	,005	1	,005	,492	,483	,001
FieldChanged	Organizational	,004	1	,004	,762	,383	,002
	Psycho-Social	,051	1	,051	5,347	,021	,010
Gender * SchoolLevel	Organizational	,004	1	,004	,703	,402	,001
	Psycho-Social	,008	1	,008	,840	,360	,002
Gender * FieldChanged	Organizational	,008	1	,008	1,575	,210	,003
	Psycho-Social	,063	1	,063	6,632	,010	,013
SchoolLevel * FieldChanged	Organizational	,000	1	,000	,052	,820	,000
	Psycho-Social	,007	1	,007	,711	,399	,001
Gender * SchoolLevel * FieldChanged	Organizational	,000	0	.	.	.	,000
	Psycho-Social	,000	0	.	.	.	,000
Error	Organizational	2,522	505	,005			
	Psycho-Social	4,796	505	,009			
Total	Organizational	183,925	512				
	Psycho-Social	160,981	512				
Corrected Total	Organizational	2,622	511				
	Psycho-Social	4,943	511				

a. R Squared = ,041 (Adjusted R Squared = ,029)

b. R Squared = ,029 (Adjusted R Squared = ,017)

MANOVA results for organizational-managerial motivation and psycho-social motivation are shown in Table 4. On the psycho-social motivation sub-dimension based on teachers' field change, there are significant differences ($F_{(1-.51)}=5.347$, $p=.021$, $\eta^2=.010$). Furthermore, on the dimension of psycho-social motivation, there are significant differences based on the gender * field change ($F_{(1-.063)}=6.632$, $p=.010$, $\eta^2=.013$). Univariate ANOVA tests could not be performed because of the fact that the variables in the study that were significant differ only in two groups. Instead, it was determined by plotting which meaningful differences are in which direction. On the psycho-social motivation sub-dimension, the teachers who did not change the field had higher job motivation compared to teachers who had made field changes and teachers working in primary schools were found to have higher job motivation than teachers working in secondary schools.

5. Conclusion, Discussion and Recommendations

In this study that we aimed to determine the job motivation levels of the primary school teachers who have changed the field due to the new education system (4+4+4) which has 12 years of compulsory education, it was found that the perceptions about the job motivation of the teachers working in primary school are higher than those in secondary school for both "organizational-managerial motivation" and "psycho-social motivation" sub-dimensions. Köprülü (2011), in his study on the relationship between organizational citizenship behaviors and motivations of primary school teachers, has found that, in general, teachers' motivation levels are higher than the average. Ertürk (2014), who investigated the relationship between teachers' job motivations and their organizational commitment, found that the job motivation of teachers was "high", especially their internal motivation perceptions.

As a result of this, there are some problems that secondary schools have such as insufficient secondary school buildings or infrastructures (inadequacy of classroom, increase of number of students, application of dual education system), while trying to become a new institution due to the transfer of primary and secondary schools as separate institutions to the premises with the new education system. Furthermore, due to the system change, it can be interpreted as the fact that many senior primary school teachers make field changes and branch teachers cannot be assigned or cannot change their place, this also reduces the motivation of teachers working in secondary school. When we analyze the findings in the framework of the goal-setting theory, it is very important for the organization managers to include the employees in the process of setting goals and to get the opinions of the employees to reach the goals of the organization. This increases the employee's commitment to goals and the desire to

achieve them. However, when the transition to the new education system is made, if the lack of infrastructure is not eliminated, teachers' opinions are not asked, the teachers who practice the system do not have enough knowledge about the new system, and the teachers lose their permanent position, the system may not reach its goals or may reach them delayed. In the literature, studies regarding the effect of school type variable on the motivation of teachers on job motivation have not often been encountered and also researches that found that there is no meaningful difference in terms of field variable (primary school and field teachers). In the research, they conducted on the teachers, Köprülü (2011), Argon and Ertürk (2013), Memişoğlu and Kalay (2017) found that there was no significant difference in motivation perceptions of the teachers based on the fields.

When the opinions of the primary and secondary school teachers participating in the research were examined, in terms of gender it was found that there was a meaningful difference in the organizational-managerial motivation sub-dimension in favor of male teachers and in the psycho-social motivation sub-dimension in favor of female teachers. In other words, while male teachers compared to female teachers think that the school management system they are working with (using their own method, working hours, compliance between managers, etc.) is more motivating, female teachers compared to males think that the institution they are working for is more motivating in terms of psychological and social (appreciation and success, vocational training and development, team work, social activities, etc.). It can be argued that this difference in the way of thinking of men and women has given the male teachers more importance to the management understanding within the organization. In this context, it is clear that in the framework of E. Locke's Goal-Setting Theory, the way that managers set clear and challenging but achievable goals for male teachers (such as raising the achievement level of school in competitions) may increase both school achievement levels and male teacher motivation. On the other hand, when considering the importance of psycho-social motivation for female teachers, it can be said that managers should take care to perform actions that motivate feelings of appreciation, success, and prestige while offering performance evaluation and feedback within the framework of Goal-Setting Theory. There are studies supporting this finding related to job motivation in literature (Bayrakdar, 2016; Demirci, 2011; Kırcı, 2013; Soykenar, 2008; Yavuz & Karadeniz, 2009). However, there are also studies in the field that find that there is no significant gender difference in terms of job motivation. Tanrıverdi (2007) on his study about the relationship between participatory school culture and language teachers' job motivation, Yılmaz (2009) on his study about influence of organizational culture on the job motivation of teachers, and Reçepoğlu (2013) on his study about teachers' job motivations in terms of different variables found that there was no gender

difference in terms of job motivation. In the literature, it can be said that there is no consensus on whether job motivation has changed based on the gender. This situation can be interpreted that the job motivation varies according to individual evaluations.

With the transition to the new system when whether the teachers losing their permanent position influenced their job motivation was examined, both organizational-managerial motivations and psycho-social motivations of teachers who changed their field were lower compared to the teachers who did not change field. In other words, the field change, which is a must for the primary school teachers after the new system, has affected the motivation of teachers negatively. In addition, both organizational-managerial motivations and psycho-social motivations of female teachers who made field changes were higher than male teachers who made changes. This can be interpreted as the fact that female teachers are more motivated to adapt to the conditions that arise due to field change. In addition, it was found that male teachers who did not change their field had higher organizational-managerial and psycho-social motivations than male teachers who made field changes. The reason why the organizational-managerial and psycho-social motivation of the primary school teachers who changed field is lower than the teachers who did not change field is that trying to give an education out of the field of graduation is very hard and creating new methods suitable for themselves by changing their usual patterns for years and trying to be more productive for the students may make teachers unhappy. Transitioning to side fields or other fields (Technology design teaching, mentally disabled teaching) may have negatively affected teachers' self-confidence. Along with this, it can be interpreted as the fact that encountering the problem of exclusion by the teachers to whose field primary school teachers transferred to might also decreased the motivation of them. As a result of the investigation, the organizational-managerial motivation levels of the male teachers who did not change the field were higher than the female teachers who did not change the field. In such result, workload of female teachers being more than male teachers and female's more detailed thinking can be effective.

Memişoğlu and Kalay (2017) found that female teachers have lower job motivation than male teachers in their study of the relationship between organizational commitment and job motivations of primary and secondary school teachers. This is interpreted as the fact that women are not fully motivated to work because they try to take care of home and work together. When the results are examined in terms of Goal-Setting Theory, it can be said that the teachers who make field changes have ambiguous goals until they adapt to new fields. Having no goals or having ambiguous goals will cause the performance of employees to be low. In addition, the performance of the teachers and the methods and techniques they use in their new fields must be evaluated accurately and effectively and feedback must be provided. Knowing that whether

teachers are approaching their goals can help them to improve the quality of their education by improving their efforts and insistence and improving or renewing the methods they use. This can also affect the motivation of teachers who have made field changes positively.

In this study, the job motivation levels of primary school teachers who had undergone field change due to the new system (4+4+4), which introduced 12 years of compulsory education in 2012, were examined. As a result of the research, the following suggestions can be made:

1. In order to make up for the shortcomings of the teachers who have changed their fields, providing updated in-service trainings to the teachers from time to time may provide them with increased confidence and improved methods and techniques they use. This can help teachers to increase their job motivation levels, and thus the quality of education.
2. This research, which is conducted at Balıkesir provincial central schools, can be carried out with wider samples by including the high school in different geographical regions. Thus, results that can be generalized can be reached.
3. New studies can be done by incorporating other variables (organizational culture, organizational commitment, organizational climate, job satisfaction, organizational justice, organizational trust, etc.) that may affect the job motivation of teachers.
4. Factors such as objectivity, psychological status, and negative attitudes toward school management or colleagues of teachers may have affected the results of the research, although the "Job Motivation" scale used had a sufficient level of validity and reliability. For this reason, the inclusion of both quantitative and qualitative studies in future can lead to more comprehensive findings.

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